

Spectrophotometric Determination of Cerium(IV) in Geological Samples after Solvent Extraction with 2-Thenoyltrifluoroacetone

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In an attempt to develop rapid and simple method, Smith¹ developed a liquid-liquid extraction method to extract radiocerium in fission products by using HTTA but no spectrophotometric studies were reported. Khopkar *et al.*² used HTTA to extract Ce^{IV} but at different parameters followed by absorbance measurement of Ce(TTA)₄ complex. There are serious interferences reported by them due to various metal ions during the extraction of Ce^{IV}. A combination of solvent extraction and ion-exchange procedures was recommended by them to get rid of these interferences and thus making the method lengthy. Moreover, the method was applied neither to real nor to synthetic samples and also the sensitivity is not enough to estimate Ce at ppm level.

The present method aims to estimate cerium present in natural samples at ppm level by liquid-liquid extraction with HTTA, followed by spectrophotometric determination with arsenazo-III after stripping the non-aqueous phase with nitric acid. The method is more selective and sensitive compared to the previous methods.

Results and Discussion

Cerium(IV) is quantitatively extracted with 0.5 M HTTA in benzene/xylene in 0.5 M H₂SO₄ medium when extracted twice for 10 min and it gets completely stripped from non-aqueous phase when shaken with equal volume of 10 M HNO₃. The notable feature is that U^{VI}, Y^{III}, La^{III}, Eu^{III}, Gd^{III}, Dy^{III}, Er^{III}, Zr^{IV} and Th^{IV} (200 µg each) do not get extracted and thus pose no problem during the spectrophotometric determination with arsenazo-III. Fe^{III} gets extracted and interferes in the final es-

timation. Its interference was obviated by pre-extraction with ether/ethyl acetate in 6 M HCl medium. Manganese also gets extracted and seriously interferes in the direct measurement method³, but in the present method it does not interfere. Presence of chloride ions at the extraction stage was avoided as it is known to reduce Ce^{VI} to Ce^{III}. However, sodium bromate was used to completely oxidise Ce^{III} to Ce^{IV} before the extraction. Phosphate, manganese, molybdenum and titanium (200 µg each) do not interfere either during extraction or determination stage. On account of poor sensitivity in direct measurement method, cerium was estimated after stripping the non-aqueous phase with 10 M HNO₃ and estimated spectro-photometrically with arsenazo-III at 660 nm. Among the various colorimetric reagents available for cerium (xylenol orange, alizarin red-S, PAR, PAN, arsenazo-I, arsenazo -III etc.), arsenazo-III was found to have the highest sensitivity.

To check the validity of the method international standard samples SY-2 and MRG-1 were analysed by the proposed method. The results are in good agreement with the reported values with relative error of ±10% (Table 1). A few geological samples were also analysed by standard addition method. Recovery of cerium down to 10 µg was found to be quantitative (>95%) and this sets the sensitivity of the proposed method. It is suited for silicate and phosphate matrices. The method is highly selective as cerium gets practically separated from all those elements which react with arsenazo-III. It is 3-4 times more sensitive than that involving direct measurement in non-aqueous phase Ce(TTA)₄.

TABLE I—ANALYSIS OF INTERNATIONAL STANDARD SAMPLES BY PROPOSED METHOD

Sample	Sample weight g	Recommended value Ce (ppm)	Value obtained* Ce (ppm)	Relative error(%)
SY-2	0.1	210	190.0	-8
MRG-1	1.0	25	23.0	-8
MRG-1	0.5	25	25.8	+3

*Mean of two values.

Recommended procedure : The geological sample (1 g) is fused with sodium peroxide (5-6 g) in nickel crucible. The melt is leached with distilled water, boiled and filtered. The residue washed with hot 5% NaOH, dissolved in minimum amount of HCl and water. The solution is evaporated to dryness, the mass leached in 6 N HCl (10 ml) and Fe^{III} extracted with ether/ethyl acetate for 2 min. The process is repeated till the organic layer becomes colourless. The aqueous phase is evaporated along with H₂O₂ (30% ; 1 ml) to remove organic matter. The residue is leached in 0.5 M H₂SO₄ (10 ml) heated to fumes of H₂SO₄, cooled, then 1 M sodium bromate (3 ml) is added, warmed on a water-bath for 10 min, cooled and made upto 10 ml with distilled water. The solution is shaken for 10 min twice with 0.5 M HTTA in benzene/xylene. The organic phase is separated and the aqueous phase discarded. Cerium is stripped with 10 M HNO₃ (10 ml) by shaking for 1 min. Organic phase is rejected and the aqueous phase is treated with H₂O₂ (30%, 1 ml) to destroy organic matter and is evaporated to dryness. The residue is treated with 1 : 1 HCl (5 ml) and evaporated to dryness. The process is repeated and the residue is leached with 0.01 M HCl (10 ml) and the solution made upto known volume. To an aliquot (containing 2.5-15 µg cerium), the KCl buffer (2.5 ml) and 0.1% arsenazo-III solution (1 ml) is added and the volume made upto 25 ml with 0.01 M HCl. Similar treatment is given to blank and standards. Absorbance is measured against blank at 660 nm. Cerium concentration is computed from the calibration curve.

Experimental

All the reagents were of A.R./G.R. grade. Stock solution of cerium was prepared from standard salt ceric ammonium sulphate (G.R./S.M., 99%) in dilute H₂SO₄ (0.5 N) and diluted to the required con-

centration (1 ml = 10 µg Ce) with 0.5 M H₂SO₄. Solutions of foreign ions were prepared by standard methods using respective reagent grade salts. Solutions of 0.5 M 2-thenoyltrifluoroacetone (Koch light) in benzene/xylene and H₂O₂ (30%) were used. KCl buffer solution (pH 1.8-2) was prepared by mixing 0.2 M HCl (80 ml) with 0.2 M KCl (250 ml) and water (670 ml). A 0.1% arsenazo-III (Merck, Pro-analyst) solution was prepared in 0.01 M HCl. A 1M aqueous sodium bromate (A.R., C.D.H.) was used.

A Varian 634 spectrophotometer was used for absorbance measurement.

Procedure : To an aliquot containing cerium (10-30 µg) having an acidity of 0.5 M with respect to H₂SO₄ was added 1 M sodium bromate (3 ml) to oxidise Ce^{III} to Ce^{IV}, then warmed on a water-bath for 10 min and the volume made upto 10 ml with 0.5 M H₂SO₄. Ce^{IV} was extracted with 0.5 M HTTA in benzene/xylene (2 × 10 ml) for 10 min. The combined phase was stripped with 10 M HNO₃ (10 ml) for 1 min to bring cerium into the aqueous phase. Completion of extraction was confirmed by estimating cerium spectrophotometrically using arsenazo-III solution at 660 nm.

In order to check the scope of the method for natural samples a study on recovery of cerium (20 µg) in presence of various associated ions was made by mixing their standard solutions separately with cerium and using the above method of extraction and determination of cerium.

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